
Whispering Shelves - Revisiting the Salar Jung Museum Library at Hyderabad in India

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ABSTRACT: Libraries have always been about book collections, connections through knowledge dissemination and knowledge preservation. Since libraries are of different kinds, it would be interesting to know how a library which is an integral part of a national level museum in India, the Salar Jung Museum at Hyderabad, under the Ministry of Culture, Government of India, is serving society over 70 years. This article traces the birth and growth of an iconic library set up by royals, the Salar Jungs, prime ministers from the erstwhile Nizam rule of Hyderabad State (1724 – 1948 A. D) in the Deccan region of India. It also examines how the library has gone from being a private collection to a public library to a 'special' library accessible to the public, been a gift to the society it serves and continues into the 21st century.

KEYWORDS: Historical libraries, Museum Libraries, History of Libraries, Salar Jung Museum Library, Indian Libraries.

INTRODUCTION: a history of the library

The Salar Jung Museum and Library of Hyderabad is a part of the rich history of Hyderabad. It is an iconic destination in Hyderabad. The major portion of this collection was acquired by Nawab Mir Yousuf Ali Khan known as Salar Jung III, who had been a prime minister in the erstwhile Nizam rule of Hyderabad State, before it joined the Indian Union in 1948. The museum is a repository of mostly decorative art of diverse European, Asian and Far Eastern countries of the world as collected by him and kept in his family palace 'Dewan Deodi', at Hyderabad. After Salar Jung III passed away in 1949, the heirs of Salar Jung III graciously agreed to donate the entire collection to the Government of India. The collection was arranged into a museum with the help of an art critic and then opened to the public by Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, the first Prime Minister of India on 16th December 1951 at the 'Dewan Deodi'. Through an Act of Parliament No.26 of 1961, the Salar Jung Museum together with the library was declared to be an 'Institution of National Importance' of India¹.

As mentioned, 'Dewan Deodi' was the ancestral mansion of the Salar Jung family who were prime ministers in the erstwhile Nizam rule. The collection of books and manuscripts was basically developed by the Salar Jung family which is one of the most illustrious in the annals of Deccan history of India. The origin of the collection dates back to 1656 A.D but it was arranged as a library by Nawab Mir Turab Ali Khan, Salar Jung I (1829-1883) and was further developed by his son Nawab Mir Laiq Ali Khan, Salar Jung II (1863-1889) and finally by his grandson, Nawab Mir Yousuf Ali Khan, Salar Jung III (1889-1949). The books and manuscripts have been thus collected over a long period of time. The inception of the collection dates back to 1656 A.D/1067 H. till the death of Salar Jung III in 1949 to total around 40,000 books and 8100 manuscripts¹. The autographs and seals found on manuscripts and Oriental books prove that the collection was developed by many generations of the Salar Jung family. The library remained at the palace but the museum objects along with its library holdings was shifted to a new building, inaugurated in July 1968 on the southern bank of the river Musi which passes through Hyderabad.

The printed books collection of the library was on various subjects covering all areas of knowledge. additions have been made after the initial Salar Jung Collection, from the grants from the Government of India, stands at 69,000 books, out of which 45,000 are in English, 15,000 in Urdu, 3600 in Persian, 2700 in Arabic and around 150 in Turkish. There are over 1500 titles in Hindi and over 1300 titles in Telugu. Collection development is a continuous process and new books are constantly being added, mostly on subjects connected with Art, History, Culture, Conservation and Museology¹¹.

METHODOLOGY: *modus operandi of the study*

This study undertakes to understand the library by finding out how the library was built up and developed and how it is serving society by looking at its collection and collection development. Another objective during the revisit of the library would be to understand how a heritage enthusiast on Hyderabad can use resources to learn about the history and heritage on the same subject

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via its different types of collections. In order to reach these goals, this chapter adopts first a 'literature survey' in highlighting some of the significant primary and secondary resources in/on the library.

SURVEY OF LITERATURE: *writings on the museum library*

There is no book published exclusively about the Salar Jung Museum's Library and published research work is less on Salar Jung Museum Library's history and role in understanding heritage. However, there have been studies on Salar Jung Museum Library and museum libraries as well. A study in 1999 by Wateren, Jan van der on the importance of museum libraries emphasises on the role of a library in a museum. He talks about co-operation between art institutions and their information resources. He notes "Museum libraries see themselves as part of an information environment at their museum. A researcher may be referred from one part of that environment to another, from the library to an office where they are compiling an inventory, or to the photo archive. But the library is the fulcrum, where the researcher can start their research and be forwarded onward. In the library there is a recognition of public service, so the researcher is more likely to be guided or helped as they formulate a research itinerary through the museum's information environment. So even if all the parts of that info environment aren't "under" the library, the library staff are the ones who have the clearest notion of the relationship between the parts and the whole" ¹².

A souvenir of Silver Jubilee Celebrations was brought in 1976, edited by Dr. M.L Nigam and published by the Salar Jung Museum itself, which has chapters on the history and collections of the Salar Jung Museum Library by Jawwad Rizvi, on printed books and Dr Rahmat Ali Khan, on the Manuscripts collection. Author Mohammad Taher has contributed a chapter: "Salar Jung Museum Library: Its Growth and Development as a Liberal University" in a book: *Studies in Librarianship* (1997). More recently Dr. Rajendra Pahade has written an article on the library in *International Journal of Science and Research* (2016). In addition to this there are few other articles published in periodicals like INTACH. The primary resources are the catalogue of the library. They are both in register, card and computer form in KOHA software which are very useful in understanding the collection. Now, let us revisit the museum library in all its glory through its collections and methods adopted to stay relevant in the 21st century.

THE SALAR JUNG COLLECTION: *voices from yore*

English Section: The collection was built up by adding new and second-hand books and also through gifts by contemporaries. Entire collections of 'jagirdars' (landlords) like Mir Gulam Ali were also purchased. Salar Jung III also acquired valuable second-hand books of the time. Many books bear the stamp of Secunderabad Club Library, Mohammedan Library, Secunderabad, Royal Asiatic Society Library, Bombay, W. H Smith and Sons subscriptions Library etc. Many were gifted by Mahboob Yar Jung Nazim-ud-daula Bahadur (1326-1908), ADC to Nizam VI, Nawab Mir Mahboob Ali Khan, to the library. Dr. Mir Yousuf Ali, surgeon to Nawab Mir Laiq Ali Khan also donated majorly to the collection. The English collection was augmented mainly during the lifetime of Salar Jung III¹. This large section covers a variety of subjects ranging Philosophy, Religion, Law, Economics, Education, History, Literature, History, Travel, Mathematics, General Sciences, Medical Sciences, Biographies, Geology, Engineering and Geography. The number of books in History are over 7000, Indian History 3600, Biography and Travel 2500. The oldest book in English is "General historie of the Turkes" by Richard Knolles, 1641 A.D.¹⁰. The collection includes translated works, prints, photo-albums and research journals. Old and antiquarian books have also been collected by the Salar Jungs. Some autographed copies include: *Leaves from the journal of our life in the Highlands 1848-1861*, autographed by Queen Victoria and gifted to Mukhtar-ul-mulk, Salar Jung I, in 1876. Another book of poems is autographed by author Sarojini Naidu, *The bird of time*, 1912¹. There are other books signed by the authors like Moulvi Chirag Ali and by some of the erstwhile Nawabs of Hyderabad (noblemen) who have donated the same to the Salar Jung family. Old and antiquarian books have also been collected by the Salar Jungs. Some autographed copies include: *Leaves from the journal of our life in the Highlands 1848-1861*, autographed by Queen Victoria and gifted to Mukhtar-ul-mulk, Salar Jung I, in 1876. Another book of poems is autographed by author Sarojini Naidu, *The bird of time*, 1912¹. There are other books signed by the authors like Moulvi Chirag Ali and by some of the erstwhile Nawabs of Hyderabad (noblemen) who have donated the same to the Salar Jung family. Translations and many antiquarian books are also part of the collection. Some translations in the library include 'Shakuntala' of Kalidas or 'Abhijnanasakuntalam' which is a beautiful tale of love and romance, it was for the very first time translated in English language by Sir William Jones in the year 1789, founder of the Asiatic Society of Bengal, Calcutta; *Ocean of stories*, *Katha Sarit Sagara* of Somadeva; *Heetopadesha* of Vishnusarma, *Razm Nama*, the Persian translation of the epic Mahabharata is known as *Razmnama* which literally means 'tale of war'. The translation work of the Mahabharata was commissioned by Mughal Emperor Akbar in 1582. *Kadambari Kathamukha*; a translation of Sanskrit work Banabhatta's *Kadambari* which is a romance in Sanskrit prose by J.S.N Chakravarthy, 1939; *Meghaduta* of Kalidasa, translated from the Sanskrit, London, OUP, 1935 by G. H Rooke, *Bahar-i-Danish*, translated by Jonathan Scott, the *Bahar-i Danish* (*Spring of Knowledge*) is a Persian collection of romantic tales. Some antiquarian titles include; *The history of America* by William Robertson D.D., 1788; *The history of Japan* by Engelbert Kaempper, 1727; *Reflections on the revolution in France* by Edmund Burke, 1790; *The present state of the Ottoman empire* by Paul Rycant, 1668; *The great fight for India* by Herbert Strang, 1757; *History of Hindustan* by Alexander Dow; *History of the life of Nadir Shah, King of Persia* by William Jones, 1773; *The philosophy of Natural History*, by William Smellie, 1790.

Figure 1: Entrance to the 'Dewan Deodi', circa 1950s.

Reference Section: The Reference section has journals, encyclopaedias, books on Museology and Conservation, Art, Archaeology and Architecture. The oldest reference book is 'Historical and critical dictionary' in four volumes by Monsieur Boyle, translated from French to English, published in 1710 A. D. The library has Asiatic Annual Registers of 1799-1811. There are volumes of "Hyderabad Affairs" compiled by Syed Mehdi Ali; a chronicle of Hyderabad, many important events are recorded which serve as a proof for scholars studying its history. This section houses journals like 'Islamic Culture' which has many important articles on the history and culture of Hyderabad-Deccan.

Oriental Section: This section has books in Urdu, Arabic, Persian and Turkish in all areas of knowledge covering various subjects including Islam, Poetry, Literature, History, Medicine among others. The number of Persian books is over 3200, Arabic over 2000. Books on religion and history number the most and books on Urdu literature number over 2100 covering classic works of prose and poetry. Biographies form an important part of the collection. The oldest book in the collection is *Tarikh-e-abul fida* in Arabic, 1723 A.D which deals with the history of the early Caliphs ¹¹.

Coming to the history of Hyderabad the section has *Tuzuk-e-asafiya* by Mir Ahmed Ali Khan Moosvi, 1892, *Maser-ul-amra* in 3 volumes by Nawab Shamsudaula Shah Nawaz Khan, 1888, *Haddeqatul Alam* in 2 volumes by Mir Abul Qasim Raziuddin Al Moosvi, 1891, *Yaadgaar-e-Makhanlal*, by Makhan Lal Juyy, 1848, *Mahboob-ul-sayer nigaristan-e-Asafiya* by Nawab Aziz Jung Bahadur, 1895, *Kitab-e-shajra-e-Asafiya* by Mouzam-ul-mulk, 1894. Some more interesting titles on Hyderabad include *Qusosyat-e-huzoor Nizam* by Syed Afzal Hussain Kantori, 1907, *Jashn-e-Osmani* by Mohammad Fazil, 1935, *Hyderabad ki talimi Taraqqi* by Abdul Qaddar Sarwari, 1934, *Deccan ki siyasi Tariq* by Syed Abdullah Moudodi, 1944, *Riyaz-e-mukhtariya* by Mir Dilawar Ali Danish, 1942².

Manuscripts Section: The collection of around 8100 manuscripts includes various media like parchment, textile, palm leaf, paper, glass, wood, and stone, different languages such as Arabic, Persian, Urdu, a few of Turkish, Dakhni, Pushtu, Hindi, Sanskrit, Telugu and Oriya and deals with many subjects. The collection also includes more than one thousand five hundred calligraphic panels and albums of miniature paintings of different schools.

The range of subjects is very wide as mentioned and includes Medicine, Science, Logic, Agriculture, Calligraphy, Lexicography, Mathematics, Physics, Astronomy, Games, Art, Syntax, Music, History, Poetry, Biography, Rhetoric, Philosophy, Etymology, Ethics, Politics, Travels, Divinations, Holy Quranic Sciences, Theology, Sufism, Law, Dictionaries, and Magic among others.

The manuscripts are related to religions including Islam, Hinduism, Christianity and Zoroastrianism. Some calligraphic panels are incised on glass, and the museum has manuscripts with excellent nail work. The other calligraphic works are in many scripts, like *Kufi*, *Thulth*, *Naskh*, *Ta'liq*, *Nasta'aliq*, *Gubar*, *Raihan*, *Shikasta*, *Diwani*, *Riqa'*, *Bahar*, *Tughra*, *Ma'akus* and in various styles.

The collection of manuscripts in Persian on the history of Hyderabad and its culture include *Tuhfa-e- mukhtariya* a history of the Qutub Shahi kings of Golconda written in 1876 on the request of Sir Salar Jung I, *Tadhkira-e-asifiyah*; a history of the early Asif Jahi dynasty on Nizam-ul-mulk Asif Jah, his son Nasir Jung, maternal grandson, Muzaffar Jung; *Tarikh-e-zafrah*, a history of the Qutub Shahi kings, Alamgir to Mohammad Alam II. Another manuscript *Sawanih-e-deccan* is a gazetteer of the six 'subahs' of the Deccan and the history of the Asif Jahi dynasty from 1724 to 1783. *Tarikh-e-Nizami*, a history of Mir Nizam Ali Khan, Nizam II compiled by Mir Alam; *Tuhfah-e-dakkan*, a history of the Deccan from the rise of the Muslim power down to 1863, compiled by Ratan Lal. *Sudad-e Haidarabad Dakkan*, a history of Hyderabad from 1853 to 1863, a period under the administration of Prime Minister, Sir Salar Jung I. This work mentions the reforms started by him which had a big influence on the History of Hyderabad. *Mah-nama* is a history of the Nizams commissioned by Mahlaqa Chanda Bai, royal courtesan at the court of Nizam Ali Khan,

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Nizam II. The work was completed in 1229 H. /1814 A.D. by Ghulam Husain Khan Jauhar⁴. Manuscripts in Urdu include the *Kuliyat-e-Sultan Mohammad Quli Qutub Shah* who ruled 988 to 1020 H, the fifth Sultan of Golconda who founded the city of Hyderabad and who was a poet in Urdu and Telugu. This is his 'diwan' or collection which consists of *ghazals* (poetry about love, God) and few *qasidas* (eulogies). The library has his *Diwan-e-Sultan Mohammad Quli Qutub Shah* from 1141 H written in beautiful gold worked *naskh* script. Another notable manuscript in Urdu is *Diwan-e Abdullah Qutub Shah* in *nastaliq* script written before 1083 H. which is his poetry in one volume¹.

Figure 2: Salar Jung I

Figure 3: Salar Jung III

ART ALBUMS AND 'MURAQQAS': the world in images

The library has art albums which are largely illustrated books or collections of paintings and calligraphic panels in the manuscripts collection. This collection includes titles published in the 19th century on views of the Deccan region; *Sketches in the Deccan* by Capt. Philip Meadows Taylor, 1837. This source throws light on the architecture prevalent in making royal structures and public buildings. The miniature paintings in the illustrated albums in the Persian collection, the 'muraqqas' include persona from the history of Hyderabad like Munir-ul-mulk Haidar Yar Khan Sher Jung, illustrious forefather of Salar Jung's smoking a 'huqqa' (hubble bubble/water pipe), Deccani school, from 12th/18th century. A painting depicts Munir-ul mulk and his son seated on a *chowki* and his son Ghuyur Jung facing him, with an attendant holding a flywhisk, Deccan school, Late 12th/18th century. There is another interesting painting showing Ruknudowlah Bahadur, the prime minister of Hyderabad seated on a *masnad* (throne made of bolsters and cushions) smoking a *huqqa*, Deccani school, 12th/18th century. Mir Nizam Ali Khan and his minister Arastu Jah are seen together with the aged Nizam on a *masnad*, (a type of throne) Deccan school, from 13th Hijri/19th century. Another depicts Munir-ul-mulk and Chandu Lal, prime minister of Hyderabad, where he is seated on *masnad* and Raja Chandu Lal is offering the *nadhar* (gift) of gold mohurs standing in front. Behind him is his son Bala Pershad, Deccan school, mid-13th H./19th century. Yet another one shows a Paigah nobleman Togh Jung Shams ul umara standing with mace over his right shoulder, also the *darbar* of Nizam Ali Khan, also painting of Sikandar Jah, the third Nizam. Also in the collection is *Khututi-e-tarikhi*, a collection of historical letters of Maharaja Chandu Lal and officers of the East India Company written between 1833 and 1837 A.D. These paintings and letters throw light on the dress and manners and life of the time of the Asaf Jahi rule of the Nizams of Hyderabad^{1,2}.

Figure 4 and 5: Illustrated manuscript with painting and calligraphic page.

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PHOTO ALBUMS: monuments and regal visits

The Golconda kingdom including the Hyderabad-Deccan saw many visitors from different places. Many travellers have come to this region on their travels to the Indian subcontinent. During the Qutub Shahi reign (1512 – 1687), diamond merchants used to come to Hyderabad as it was the only centre in the world. The famous merchant Jean Baptiste Tavernier has left accounts of his travels who visited Hyderabad twice in 1648 and in 1652. Some other European travellers include Jean de Thevenot who visited in 1665-6. Francois Bernier visited in 1687. The library has copies of travelogues written by them². During the Nizam era, the Viceroy and Governor Generals of India appointed by the British Government visited the state of Hyderabad-Deccan. Lord Elgin in 1895, Lord Curzon in 1902, The Prince of Wales in 1906, Lord Minto in 1907, Lord Hardinge in 1911, The German Crown Prince Friedrich Wilhelm in 1911, Lord Willingdon in 1933, Lord Linlithgow in 1938; have visited as state guests. The library has photo albums of the royal visits photo-chronicled by Raja Deen Dayal (b. 1844 –d 1905 A.D), the official photographer to the Nizam and later albums by his firm Raja Deen Dayal and Sons². Raja Deen Dayal has also photographed many monuments of the region which serve a proof of the art and architecture for historians and researchers. The photos of the monuments which include Golconda views, the Charminar, the Qutub Shahi tombs among others are of great interest to the local press, the history enthusiasts, scholars and conservation architects. The photos give an idea about the monuments as they looked at the end of the 19th century and the royal visit images show the protocols followed during reception of state guests during the era on the VIth and VIIth Nizam of Hyderabad State in British India (1857-1947 A.D) and the dress and manners of the royals and noblemen as well.

Figure 6: The Residency, Hyderabad, 1880s.

Figure 7: Visit of Lord Curzon, 1902.

LATER COLLECTIONS AND UPGRADES: moving with the times

Collection Management – New books have been added to the library since it moved to the new building from ‘Dewan Deodi’ where it was kept till mid-1968. Some titles which have been included as part of collection development are *Hindu view of art* by Mulk Raj Anand, 1957, *Modern art movements*, Trewin Coplestone, 1971; *The Marwar murals* by R. A Agrawala, 1977, *The Oriental obsession: Islamic inspiration in British and American art and architecture 1500-1920* by John Sweetman, 1991, *Krishna: living God of Braj* by D. Anand, 1992; *Terracottas of North India* by S.C Kala, 1993; *Unique art of Worli paintings* by Sudha Satyawadi, 2010; *Live textiles: a practical approach to understand fabrics* by Akshay Tholia, 2009, *Made for Mughal Emperors: royal treasures from Hindustan* by Susan Stronge, 2010, *The Maharajas and their magnificent motor cars* by Gautam Sen, 2011; *Princes and painters in Mughal Delhi 1707-1857* by William Dalrymple and Yuthika Sharma, eds., 2012; *Glass making in England* by J. Harry Powell, 2014, *The economy of the Mughal empire* by Shireen Moosvi, 2015, *The Ramayana* by Lakshmi Lal, 2016, *The care of prints and drawings* by Margaret Holben Ellis, 2017, *The conservation movement- a history of architectural preservation* by Miles Glendinning, 2018, *Archaeology of Eastern India* by Rajendra Dehuri, 2019, *The Anarchy* by William Dalrymple, 2020, *A sacred journey - The Kedara Kalpa series of Pahari paintings & the painter Purkhu of Kangra* by B.N Goswamy, 2021 among many others².

Digitisation – Over 28,000 rare, old books of English, Urdu, Persian and Arabic of the library have been digitized and are on intranet for access by users of the library¹⁴. The titles are being uploaded on indiaculture.gov.in, a portal developed and managed by Ministry of Culture, Govt. of India. Digitisation gives access to all people across the globe cutting across national boundaries. The manuscripts are also being digitised for easier access by readers. For the security of the books, RFID system has been implemented integrating with the library software KOHA.

ROLE IN SOCIETY: a knowledge seeker’s space

Service to readers - The library has been serving scholars and readers from different countries for the last 70 years through its reference and other services and moves on to the future with existing books, journals, more new titles and e-resources. The books and resources on Hyderabad will be further augmented and utilised by the reading public to discover and understand un-discovered facets of this heritage city and enrich the existing knowledge¹³.

The readership has its own history. The library at ‘Dewan Deodi’ had the noblemen (Nawabs) including the Nizam (ruler of the State) borrowing books. The Nawabs were fond of reading and read on a variety of subjects as the collection represented many

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subjects³. Later, on the passing away of Salar Jung III and the library being opened to the public many others got access to the collection. The library did away with the lending system and became closed access due to the collection having many rare and precious out of print books. Today it is still closed access, mainly a 'Reference Library' where scholars and readers sit and do their study and research. The collection has grown from 40,000 to 69,000 printed books by acquisitions to the initial collection. The digitised books are available for readers on intranet. The focus of later collections is mainly books on Museology, Art history, Indian Culture and its allied areas, History of India, Craft histories and books relating to the art collection in the Salar Jung Museum. This facilitates many studies connected to the History of Hyderabad, Museology and aspects of Art history for those pursuing masters level research and Ph.D. studies.

Figure 8: Salar Jung Museum & Library, Hyderabad as it looks in the 21st century.

A cultural cosmos - Hyderabad's history and heritage through resources at the library

Given the cosmopolitanism and character of Hyderabad, its history and culture has evoked great interest among the readers from different countries. The city has people from different regions who have migrated here from different regions of Deccan India and even Africans who were part of the Nizam's army. There has been an amalgamation which gives a different flavour to the language and customs. One can see the medley of influences of Telangana, Maharashtra, Karnataka and Hyderabad rulers Qutub Shahi and Asaf Jahi kings who had Persian/mid-eastern roots⁸. The city not only has 400 plus years of history, amazing monuments, but has also been one of the first princely states in India to have its own radio, postal system, observatory, telephone and education for women^{5,8}. The cuisine of the city is also very typical and very interesting as it has imbibed influences from different cultures. The 'biryani' of Hyderabad is a great delicacy. There are different types of gravies, kebabs and breads as well⁹.

Also, the city had its own Archaeological department set up during Nizam rule. The records of the city show a very high level of documentation. A healthcare system was in place during the Qutub Shahi times (1512- 1687) which had a house of healing called the 'Dar-ul-shifa' where people came for Unani treatment. There is a lot of interest by scholars both local and international to learn about this fascinating city, its culture and manners and of course its history.

How does the Salar Jung Museum and Library help in understanding this fascinating city? A city where people from all communities and different languages have been living for years? A city that has its own dialect 'Dakhni', manners, typical cuisine, monuments, history, art and culture? It is being achieved through its resources being made available to any history and heritage enthusiast. Scholars travel from the U.S.A, Europe and other countries for studying the books and manuscripts housed here. Hyderabad also had a unique miniature painting school which evolved in the 'Asaf Jahi' Hyderabad court of the Nizams. The museum has a collection of these of which some are displayed in the Miniature Paintings Gallery at the museum, others kept in the museum storage and as part of the 'Illustrated manuscripts' of the Manuscripts collection as already cited.

An important source on the History of Hyderabad –

Pictorial Hyderabad by Krishnaswamy Mudiraj (published in 1929)

Korvi Krishnaswamy Mudiraj (25 August 1893 – 19 December 1967) was an activist, former Hyderabad mayor, writer, journalist and educator. He was the Hyderabad City Mayor for the year 1957–1958. He was born on 25 August, 1893 in Aurangabad and completed his education from the Nizam's college, Hyderabad. He obtained his higher education in Publishing Technology from Bombay. He was elected four times and served as the Municipal Councillor for 25 years from the 'Chudi Bazar' area in the city. Korvi Krishna Swamy Mudiraj was writer, journalist, educationist and leader but is more well-known as the writer of 'Pictorial Hyderabad', a masterpiece on Hyderabad under the Asaf-jahi rulers (1724 to 1929). He worked a lot in education for the Mudiraj community and other weaker sections of the city. He compiled the book 'Pictorial Hyderabad in 2 volumes'¹⁵. This book is a classic work on the history of Hyderabad-Deccan in India. It highlights the Asaf Jahi period's history up to 1920s and gives biographical

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accounts of the noblemen and royals of the time, listing all major monuments and buildings of importance in Hyderabad⁷. A great resource for scholars and people and history enthusiasts on Hyderabad and Deccan history of India, the book has proved to be a classic work over time.

The library houses the publications of the museum as well. The museum has brought out 40 volumes of its Bi-annual Research Journal. These journals have several researches on Hyderabad and throws light on its art, architecture, manners and culture. The journals are available for study in the library for the scholarly community. To cite a few articles on Hyderabad history and heritage – *A brief history of the Salar Jung* S.M. Jawwad Razvi, 1976, *Charminar – its historicity and archaeology* by W.H Siddique, 1989, *Cultural synthesis in the Qutub Shahi kingdom* by Sadiq Naqvi, 1983, *Dakhni – its origin and development*, A.S.M Quadri, 1983, *Historical mosques of Hyderabad* by N.N Krishna Sastry, 1984, *Chequered career of Chudderghat - men , matters and mansions* by K.S.R Murthy, 1989, *Asaf Jahi art – visual documents of social history* by Dr. D. N Varma, 1987, *Development of Unani Tibb during the Asaf Jahi period*, K.A Shafaqat Azmi and M.M Ali Khan, 1987, *Gateways and kamans of Hyderabad city*, by Mohammad Abdul Qaiyum, 1989, *Court life of Asaf Jahi period* by Dr. Hasnuddin Ahmed, 1991, *Hyderabad in the early 19th century* by Dr. Vandana Kaushik, 1991, *Deccani arts and crafts during the Asaf Jahi period* by Dr. D. N Varma, 1993, *Biographical sketches of Salar Jung* by Mir Taqi Ali Khan, 1995, *Hyderabad – old architectural glory* by Abid Hussain Khan, 1997, *Diamond trade in Golconda*, K.S R Murthy, 1999, *Himroo fabrics of Hyderabad* by Dr. Suguna Sarma, 1999 and so on².

Some important titles on the history of Hyderabad include *Glimpses of the Nizams' Dominion* by Claude Campbell, 1898, *Hyderabad under Sir Salar Jung I* by Moulvi Chirag Ali, 1885, *Landmarks of the Deccan* by Syed Ali Asgar Bilgrami, 1927, *Hyderabad – a city in history* by Raza Ali Khan, 1986, *Hyderabad 400 Years 1591-1991* by Raza Ali Khan, 1991, *Hyderabad – 400 glorious years* by K. Chandriah, 1998, *Portrait of a city* by Noopur Kumar, 2006, *Hyderabad – a biography* by Narendra Luther, 2006, *The splendour of Hyderabad- the last phase of an Oriental culture 1591-1948 A.D.* by Dr. M. A Nayeem, 2002, *A princely legacy-Asifiya cuisines*, by Zahid Ali, Khan, ed., 2013 among many others².

CONCLUSION: on to the future

After the process of checking and analysis of the collection, we see a thriving library where the past and present co-exist and reveal its dynamism in serving the general public and its researching readers as well. A reader could be a person from the public looking to understand both local and global history/art history and art historic movements or an independent researcher writing an article on a topic or a focussed researcher working on his paper or dissertation or Ph.D. thesis, especially on history and art history. The library also serves the Press and officials from the Government departments dealing with heritage and its conservation. The library moves on to the future with continuous additions and a hope to serve better.

REFERENCES

- 1) Nigam, M.L ed., *Silver Jubilee souvenir of Salar Jung Museum* (Hyderabad: Salar Jung Museum Board.1976). 1-18, 85-100.
- 2) Catalogues of Salar Jung Museum Library (printed Sections- primary source)
- 3) Issue records of the Salar Jung Museum Library (primary source)
- 4) Ashraf, Mohammad, comp. A catalogue of the Persian manuscripts Vol I, (Hyderabad: Salar Jung Museum 1965). 415-456
- 5) Khan, Raza Ali: *Hyderabad 400 years 1591-1991*, (Hyderabad: Zenith Services,1990). 15-215
- 6) Taher, Mohammad: *Salar Jung Museum Library: Its Growth and Development as a Liberal University*,"Studies in Librarianship. v.1. (New Delhi, Anmol Publications, 1997) pp. 113-125
- 7) Mudiraj, Krishnaswamy: *Pictorial Hyderabad* in 2 volumes, (Secunderabad, The Chandrakanth Press,1929). Vol I: i-iv
- 8) Rao, Subba, C.V: *Hyderabad: the social context of industrialisation 1875-1948*. (New Delhi: Orient Longman, 2007). 3-16
- 9) Khan, Zahid Ali, ed.: *A princely legacy-Asifiya cuisines*, (Hyderabad: The Siasat Daily 2013), 5-6,
- 10) Pahade, Rajendra, "A Study of Salar Jung Museum Library, Hyderabad", International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR) Volume 5 Issue 7, July 2016, 2193 - 2198
https://www.ijsr.net/search_index_results_paperid.php?id=ART2016751,
- 11) Ghosh, Soma: *Leaves from the past: a profile of Salar Jung Museum Library*, (Hyderabad: INTACH Annual, Hyderabad Chapter, 2016). 37-39
- 12) Wateren, Jan van der, *The importance of museum libraries*, (INSPEL, 1999) 190-198
<https://archive.ifla.org/VII/d2/inspel/99-4wajv.pdf>
- 13) Mohammed, Taher, ed: *Handbook of Research on the Role of Libraries, Archives, and Museums in Achieving Civic Engagement and Social Justice in Smart Cities* (Pennsylvania: IGI Publishing 2021) 103-120
- 14) Murali Prasad, M.R et al eds.: *Library practices in Digital era: Festschrift in honour of Prof. V. Vishwamohan - Hybrid bibliotheque: Salar Jung Museum Library*, (Hyderabad: B S Publications, 2018) 288-293

Whispering Shelves - Revisiting the Salar Jung Museum Library at Hyderabad in India.

- 15) <https://www.thehindu.com/todays-paper/tp-national/tp-andhrapradesh/mudiraj-a-multifaceted-personality/article3756500.ece> (accessed 17.02.2023)
- 16) Figures 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6,7 and 8 are Courtesy: Salar Jung Museum, Hyderabad, Telangana State, INDIA